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Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

DELIVERABLE 2.4 – USE CASE SPECIFICATION (FINAL VERSION)

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Executive summary

In this project, use cases are defined as descriptions of how a person who uses a process, or a system will accomplish an objective or a task. These use cases outline a system's behaviour from a user's point of view as it responds to a request and is represented as a sequence of steps.

This deliverable includes the final definition of the use cases. This is based on the experiences gained and developments performed within the first half of the project. It will present the final versions of the use case specifications. All the use cases are described together with XR extensions that are added/investigated during the design phase for the solutions and their scenarios. This will demonstrate how the different situations unfold with the aid of XR interaction.

The three different use cases (snow grooming, logistics and construction) defined within the THEIA^{XR} project are introduced and described in detail in this document. For each use case, a dedicated chapter (Section 0 to Section 0) within the deliverable is available. There we also describe the utilization of user stories to describe especially operator's role in the process. User stories are centred on the result and the benefit of the thing what is described, whereas use cases can be more granular, and describe how the system will act. In Section 6 we are concluding results of this deliverable.

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History of Version Updates

Nr.	Update compared to the first version of the deliverable	Partner
1.	Updates in UC1.1	PRIN
2	Slight Updates in UC1.3	PRIN
3	Removal of Chapter 3.7 avoiding redundancy with deliverable D2.5	All
4	Removal of Chapter 4.7 avoiding redundancy with deliverable D2.5	All
5	Update XR flow UC3.3	TUD
6	Removal of Chapter 5.7 avoiding redundancy with deliverable D2.5	All

1 Introduction

This document specifies the domain-specific use cases within the THEIA^{XR} project. Pilot systems associated with three different domains were selected from the field of off-highway and logistics mobile machinery. These three heterogeneous use cases pose in part similar and differing requirements on information presentation to the machine operators. The expert-driven use case analysis reported in this deliverable examines the individual potential value of applying eXtended Reality technologies for presenting data in a new, advanced, and intuitive manner to the human operator. Analysis highlights several critical operation situations. Based on the decomposition of operator workflows and information requirements, the added value and quality of data representation and interaction in extended reality means is discussed in the context of increasing the human-machine collaboration. Selected domain-specific machine types, the kind of environments they are working in, operation situations and environmental conditions are shortly described in this document .

In this document selected operation situations (use cases) are described in detail based on data collection with a formalized questionnaire to collect domain-specific knowledge on within the several domain experts in the consortium. The questionnaire focuses on involved machine and production processes, associated tasks, involved stakeholders, machine functionalities, information, and environmental constraints. The collected data is used to identify and further specify the potential of implementing of XR technologies in human-machine interaction by means of improved information availability, increased usability and suitability to existing task flows and system constraints. In the context of assessed task-based information requirements. The use case specifications have been the basis for WP3, 4 and 6. Additionally, collected domain and use case specific operation challenges are discussed, revealing differences regarding feedback and control requirements for cabin-based and teleoperation environments but highlight strong similarities regarding environmental detection, implementation of data from digital terrain and object modelling. Findings provide a basis for the applicability of the solutions in potential other domains.

In the snow groomer use cases the main objective is to supply the operator with the needed information in the best possible and digestible way, to find a solution to drive in a complete “white out” (no view to the environment possible) with sensor and visualization assistance. The use case addresses a human-mobile machinery interaction task in a very challenging environment, with most often limited visibility to the human operator. The use case considers the operator sitting in a snow groomer cabin and it will also contribute ultimately to remote controlled or supervised operation of future snowgroomers, whereby the human operator is interacting with the machine from a remote location.

In the logistics use case the main objective is to support the teleoperator to have a better perception of the task at hand and its context as it can vary from task to task. Also, how digital experience can help in this. Sub-objectives are:

- (1) Defining the most suitable set of combinations of controls which are ideal for precision, performance, and ergonomics.
- (2) To validate factors in a working environment which could be helping operators to concentrate better on their work.
- (3) Defining factors which are affecting desirability of the job.

The use case considers the teleoperator sitting in a control room in an office-like space, but it will also contribute ultimately to cabin controlled and assisted operation of a reachstacker.

In the construction use cases, the main objective is to provide interfaces to the operator for handling digital design models and their implementation in an efficient and safe way. As a result, different feedback and interaction modalities are evaluated and compared in realistic test environments. Overall, an HMI-concept for operators of highly automated excavators based on mixed-reality technology will be developed.

This document gives a brief introduction into the methodology of data assessment, documentation, and evaluation (Chapter 2), followed by a detailed documentation of use case descriptions (system description,

actor description, use case analysis, use case diagrams and derived user stories (Chapters 3, 4 and 5) and a conclusion of this deliverable (Chapter 6).

2 Methodology

2.1 Use Case data collection

While conventional human-machine interfaces (HMI) rely on visual terminal-based UI and direct environment monitoring, Extended Reality technologies offer novel forms of information presentation. Utilizing XR multimodal and augmenting information presentation techniques offers the potential to implement digitally enhanced information spaces more intuitively and effectively embedded into the operator's information perception and processing workflows in machine operation. To use XR technology where it is needed, we conducted an analysis of user workflows within the given use cases to investigate information requirements and operation specific constraints. As a result, we derived user stories that list prioritized information requirements for involved stakeholders.

To collect related domain-specific information we used a template that was developed by the OEM partners, refined by human-machine interaction experts within the project consortium. For each domain we collected data on at least three different operation scenarios covering typical tasks, machine setups and environmental conditions with a focus on problematic operation situations.

We used the template to collect data on involved machines, involved stakeholders, task goal, success criteria, frequency of occurrence in daily work shifts, pre- and post-task conditions, workflows and how workflow can be enriched with XR. This data was used to collect HMI related challenges and problems with a focus on beneficial XR techniques. The template documents workflows as a sequence of information retrieval, use and human-machine-environment interaction activities highlighting operators' information dependencies within the selected scenarios.

The result was documented in UML use case-diagrams that visualize operators' interactions with the machine HMI. Further user stories were used to extract information requirements that formulate direct requirements for potential integration of XR technology.

These results were used in the following work packages. In WP 4 useful implementation areas and conditions for XR technologies within the use cases were retrieved and specified. In WP3 suitable involvement methods for information presentation co-design were derived and in WP 5 suitable XR technologies will be focused based on these findings.

The assessed workflow descriptions, use case diagram and user stories enabled a holistic and comparable elaboration of information and interaction requirements for user interfaces with a focus on extending techniques and technologies.

2.2 Use Case Diagram notation

In the Unified Modelling Language (UML), a use case diagram can summarize the details of the system's users (also known as actors) and their interactions with the system. To build one, user utilize a set of specialized symbols and connectors which are depicted in the following Figure 1.

Figure 1: Use case Diagram notation

2.3 User Stories

As a result of the use case analysis, the user stories document a prioritized list of information requirements across use cases. It allows a cross-domain comparison of requirements indicating areas of conjoined HMI requirements that can be supported with similar XR solutions.

These compact insights were used in WP 4 to further detail information characteristics and the development of XR user interfaces and in WP 5 to explore suitable XR technology implementations that will merge into interactive XR use case demonstrators that showcase beneficial effects of XR for operators.

3 Use case 1 – Snow grooming

3.1 Description of the system

Generally, snow grooming is the process to prepare, build and maintain any kind of slope or road out of snow. A snow groomer (

) is a tracked vehicle, which is equipped with an operator cabin, a blade, a tiller and optionally with a winch. The blade on the front is used for dozing the snow, shaping slope contours, and pre-processing the snow. The tracks allow the snow groomer to drive on snowy and icy surface, so they give traction and stability to the snow groomer. With the tiller in the back, you finally process the snow so that in the end you get a long-lasting snow surface. The winch on the top is used for operations in steep terrain.

Figure 2: Snow groomer during operation ©PRINOTH

Mainly the work needs to be performed outside and on every weather condition during winter months. A skiing day starts in the morning, this requires work to be performed mostly during night.

State of the art technology allow the operator to control and interact with the vehicle in CAN-controlled systems and give permanent feedback on the chosen settings and status of vehicle sub-systems, such as engine, tiller, and winch.

As trend for efficiency, digital systems like telemetric-based fleet management and snow measurement (Figure 3) are getting more and more common in ski resorts. Specially the knowledge of the amount of snow and where to bring it is key for a successful slope management. The system uses GNSS in combination with RTK technology for identifying the position of the vehicle to an accuracy of 2-3 cm. This position is compared to a predefined terrain model, which can be based on the ground scan of the area or a computer-generated target geometry on the slope or snow terrain park. The offset below the vehicle represents the amount of snow.

Figure 3: Principle of GNSS RTK snow measurement ©PRINOTH

To bring the operator in a position to act proactively, a measurement not only under the vehicle but also underneath the blade is key. So, he can identify based on a color-coded heat map of the last recorded snow height data decide how to work with the snow and distribute it accordingly.

Within the snow groomer use case we considered three scenarios:

- Build slope matching target surface,
- obstacles detection, and
- zero sight navigation.

The following tables report on the collected data on involved agents, workflows, and user stories.

3.2 Names and descriptions of the actors

The operation of snow groomers relies on several agents. Table 1 gives an overview about the involved human and technological agents.

Name of the actor	Description
An operator	operates a snow groomer and all its accessories.
A chief of operation	is responsible for the fleet and snow management within a ski resort. He/she decides onto the work target.
A surface creator	provides a graphical 3D model, which consists of available terrain information and requirements.
A predefined obstacle	is a known static object in the operating area of the snow groomer.
An unexpected obstacle	is a dynamic object (e.g., a skier) that can occur within the area of operation.
A snow measurement system	is capturing the actual exact position (via GNSS + RTK) of a snow groomer on a slope. Combining the collected data with the existing data from the terrain scan, the actual snow depth can be calculated.
An object detection system	is analysing the surrounding and detecting obstacles within its scanning radius.

Table 1: Names and descriptions of the actors UC1

3.3 Snow groomer use cases

3.3.1 Use Case 1.1

The use case „Build Slope Matching Target Surface” (Table 2: Snowgroomer Use Case 1.1 – Build slope matching target surface

) describes which activities are required from which actor to create a surface that corresponds to the target surface. First, the chief of operation must define his requirements on the target surface and align with the surface creator. Out of the defined requirement (e.g., Snowpark) the surface creator designs the georeferenced target surface and uploads it to the snow measurement system within a snow groomer. This snow measurement system compares the measured actual surface with the target and shows via a UI (**Error! Reference source not found.**) the difference to the operator. Finally, the operator has to execute actions to reach the target surface. The use case is depicted as a use case diagram in Figure 7.

Use case name	build slope matching target surface
Use case number	1.1
Summary description	Visualization of needed information and actions to reach target surface
Status	V1
Stakeholders/actors (primary actor bolded)	1. Operator
	2. chief of operation
	3. surface creator
	4. snow measurement system
Use case goal	finished slope matches target surface
Frequency of occurrence	daily
Preconditions	1. target surface inc. tolerance and actualization based on snow situation
	2. snow depth system (e.g. GNSS + RTK, area summer scan, kinematic sensors)
	3. actual slope shape (e.g. stereo camera, LIDAR)
	4. Guideline principles for grooming (uphill, downhill, side hill, max height in 1 operation step, window...)
	5. HMI system
Post-Condition(s)	target surface matched and recorded
Basic flow	1. start-up system
	2. positioning and tracking of vehicle
	3. vehicle enters area with target surface
	4. analysis of delta from actual to target surface
	5. execution by operator to reach target
	6. record result / new actual surface
	7. share new actual surface with other vehicles and to cloud
	8. vehicle exit area
Alternative flow(s)	1. Operator / system over / under compensates
Exceptions	-
Success Criteria	Operator is informed about fulfilment rate
	Operator is willing to fulfil and to follow instructions from system
	How to visualize the information

Challenges and Problems	Not to be distractive to the operator
-------------------------	---------------------------------------

Table 2: Snowgroomer Use Case 1.1 – Build slope matching target surface

XR Flow - How situation unfolds with XR interaction

Advanced flow	1. start up system
	2. positioning and tracking of vehicle
	3. vehicle enters area with target surface
	4. indicate to operator that system is activated (XR or trad.)
	5. analysis of delta from actual to target surface
	6. use XR-technology to visualize actual and target surface
	7. use XR-technology to inform about deviations and action required to reach target along estimated vehicle trajectory
	7.1 Haptics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use kinesthetic feedback in the track controls to guide the operator towards the correct position, alignment and velocity of the vehicle • Use kinesthetic feedback in the primary joystick to guide the operator towards the ideal height and angle of the blade • The operator is not constrained to the pre-planned trajectory or ideal profile, he/she can adapt but an active movement against the kinesthetic feedback is needed. • The kinesthetic and tactile feedback adapts to the control mode chosen by the operator (front blade, etc)
	8. execution by operator / system <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8.1 Depending on the task at hand, the primary joystick provides additional degrees-of-freedom (DoF) to enable more ergonomic tool control (see input control schemes proposed in deliverable D4.4)
	9. record result / new actual surface and operator / system action
	10. share new actual surface with other vehicles and to cloud (XR-technology)
	11. inform about fulfilment rate (XR in the snow groomer, office PC...)
12. indication vehicle exit area (XR or trad.)	
Alternative flow(s)	1 toggable vibrotactile feedback in the track control or primary joystick handles can indicate the error/malfunction
	2. System malfunction indicate to operator
	3. Additional control axes can be allocated for more intuitive operation (e.g. substitution for buttons)
	4. Operator / system over-/ undercompensates
	5 visualization fulfilment rate outside specified tolerance

Table 3: XR Flow for Snowgroomer Use case 1.1

Figure 4: Snowgroomer interface touch screen for snow measurements ©PRINOTH

Figure 5: Touch screen showing a 3D park model target surface ©PRINOTH

Figure 6: Touch screen showing top, side and blade view ©PRINOTH

3.3.2 Use Case 1.2

The use case “Obstacles Detection” (Table 4) describes the required activities to avoid collisions during operation. The full visibility to the surrounding of a snow groomer is not realizable by design. Assistant systems like cameras help the operator to widen the field of visibility. Even using all systems to the best of their ability, collisions still occur. In the working area of a snow groomer there are static obstacle that are known (e.g., snow gun, pillar, pit, crevasse...) and there appear unexpected dynamic obstacles (e.g., skier). The object detection system detects known and unexpected objects and informs/warn the operator in case of a potential risk. The operator permanently observes the surrounding and checks the inputs from the system. In most of the cases with this information the operator sets corrective actions to avoid a collision. The use case is depicted as a use case diagram in Figure 9.

Use case name	obstacles detection
Use case number	1.2
Summary description	Inform about obstacles that are met during operation - predefined or unexpected (e.g., skiers, animals, trees, rocks, buildings, other vehicles on the slope, winch cable, snow pile...)
Status	V1
Stakeholders/actors (primary actor bolded)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Operator 2. surface creator 3. predefined or unexpected obstacles 4. chief of operation 5. object detection system
Use case goal	Inform the human operator about obstacles
Frequency of occurrence	permanent
Preconditions	1. virtual ski area representation (slopes including snow height info, boundaries, buildings, obstacles, height and width limitation, anchor points...)

	2. GNSS, better with RTK
	3. obstacle detection system
	4. guideline principles for grooming (uphill, downhill, side hill, max height in 1 operation step, windrow...)
	5. HMI system
Post-Condition(s)	Early warning in case of detection to avoid collision
Basic flow	1. start-up system
	2. positioning and tracking of vehicle
	3. active connection to cloud or other vehicles to get/share actual (static) surrounding information
	4. obstacle detection system active
	5. warning to operator in case of obstacle or boundary proximity
	6. execution by operator / system
Alternative flow(s)	4a. Warning to operator if system failure
Exceptions	-
Success Criteria	Detection and visualization of obstacles
Challenges and Problems	Travel speed (relevant for reaction time)
	Not to be distractive to the operator
	How to inform about the information
	Moving obstacles might continue moving, also after detection.
	No detection because of snow or ice

Table 4: Use Case 1.2: Obstacles detection

XR Flow - How situation unfolds with XR interaction

Advanced flow	1. startup system
	2. positioning and tracking of vehicle
	3. active connection to cloud or other vehicles to get/share actual (static) surrounding information
	4. obstacle detection system active
	5. visualize surrounding including real time obstacles to operator (XR technology)
	6. warning to operator in case of obstacle or boundary proximity
	6.1.Haptics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use kinesthetic feedback in the track control handles to guide the operator away from the collision course or boundary • Use vibrotactile feedback in the track control handles to alert the operator of boundary crossings • Use vibrotactile feedback in the track controls to alert the operator to the presence of and distance to an obstacle
	7. execution by operator / system
	7.1. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A toggle on the primary joystick enables switching to control of the smart spotlight to inspect or highlight obstacles.
8. record action and surrounding data	

	9. share recorded data with other vehicles and cloud (XR or trad.)
Alternative flow(s)	1a. Warning to operator if system failure 1a.1. Haptics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Togglable vibrotactile feedback notify system failures

Table 5: XR Flow for Use case 1.2

Figure 7: Potential scenario of a snowgroomer operator view using XR-technology ©PRINOTH

3.3.3 Use Case 1.3

The environmental condition influences the snowgrooming operation. In the worst case it causes a complete “White out” (no view to the environment possible). The operator still needs to perform his activities without bringing him or any other in dangerous situation. The use case “Zero Sight Navigation” describes the required activities in this critical situation. This use case presupposes use case 1.1 and 1.2. as functional and implemented. The systems need to perform also with no direct view. The operator needs to fully trust the input of the system and set the required action accordingly. The use case is depicted as a use case diagram in Figure 10.

Use case name	zero sight navigation
Use case number	1.3
Summary description	navigation under no-sight condition
Status	V1
Stakeholders/actors (primary actor bolded)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Operator 2. surface creator (PRINOTH CONNECT TEAM) 3. chief of operation 4. unexpected object (living or dead) 5. object detection system
Use case goal	system supplies navigation and surrounding information to compensate zero sight situation

Frequency of occurrence	depending on weather situation
Preconditions	1. virtual ski area representation (slopes inc. snow height info, boundaries, buildings, obstacles, height and width limitation, anchor points...)
	2. GNSS, better with RTK
	3. Zero sight obstacle detection system
	4. guideline principles for grooming (uphill, downhill, side hill, max height in 1 operation step, windrow...)
	5. HMI system
Post-Condition(s)	vehicle reaches desired end position without collision and the most appropriate way uploading of registered data
Basic flow	1. start-up system
	2. positioning and tracking of vehicle
	3. active connection to cloud or other vehicles to get/share actual surrounding information
	4. obstacle detection system active
	5. vehicle enters area with zero sight
	6. warning to operator in case of obstacle or boundary proximity
	7. execution by operator / system
Alternative flow(s)	-
Exceptions	-
Success Criteria	Provide enough information to the operator to navigate under no-sight condition
Challenges and Problems	How to visualize the information distorted by environmental influences (snow, fog, snowstorm...)
	Not to be distractive to the operator
	Full reliability to the system

Table 6: Use Case 1.3: Zero sight navigation

XR Flow - How situation unfolds with XR interaction

Advanced flow	1. startup system
	2. positioning and tracking of vehicle
	3. active connection to cloud or other vehicles to get/share actual surrounding information
	1. obstacle detection system active
	2. vehicle enters area with zero sight
Advanced flow Alternative flow(s)	3. inform about surrounding including real time obstacles to operator (XR-technology) 3.1. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> See points in use case 1.2 "Obstacle detection" for the contribution of haptics
	4. warning to operator in case of obstacle or boundary proximity (XR-technology) 4.1. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> See points in use case 1.2 "Obstacle detection" for the contribution of haptics

	5. execution by operator / system
	6. record path and surrounding data
	7. share data with other vehicles and cloud
Alternative flow(s)	
	1a. New concept for controlling direction/speed with force-feedback joystick

Table 7: XR Flow for Use case 1.3

3.4 Use case diagrams

Figure 8: Use case Diagram for “Snowgroomer Use Case 1.1 - Build slope matching target surface”

Figure 9: Use case Diagram for “Snowgroomer Use Case 1.2 - Obstacle detection”

Figure 10: Use case Diagram for “Snowgroomer Use Case 1.3 - Zero sight navigation”

3.5 User stories

ID	PRIORITY	AS A [type of user]	I NEED TO [do some task]	SO THAT I CAN [get some result]	STATUS	UC 1.1	UC 1.2	UC 1.3
1.1	Must have	Operator	get a clear indication of the system status	rely on the functionality or understand malfunction	Open	x	x	x

1.2	Must have	Operator	operate the blade, tracks, winch and the tiller according to the topography and the snow condition	get a perfect target slope prepared	Open	x	x	x
1.3	Must have	Operator	control the front blade	smooth/shape the surface	Open	x		
1.4	Must have	Operator	observe the area x meters ahead	plan and set action to achieve my target surface	Open	x		
1.5	Must have	Operator	observe the area x meters ahead	plan and set action to avoid collisions and accidents	Open		x	x
1.6	Must have	Operator	monitor the vehicle traction	set corrective action in speed and steering to prevent stopping and surface damage	Open	x	x	x
1.7	Must have	Operator	know where other vehicles are located	plan and set actions to increase efficiency and to avoid collisions/incidents	Open	x	x	x
1.8	Must have	Operator	know if and where a winch vehicle is anchored	avoid entering in dangerous area	Open	x	x	x
1.9	Should have	Operator	know where mobile snow guns are in functions	avoid collisions with water hoses or cables	Open		x	x

Table 8: User stories for Snowgroomer Use Cases

3.6 Issues

The following issues have been depicted:

- How to visualize the required information to the operator?
- Due to limited view around the vehicle, it is hard to see/detect obstacles around.
- Operator needs to work also in complete “whiteout” with no view.
- With no view it is not possible to detect obstacles with the eyes.

4 Use case 2 – Logistics

4.1 Description of the system

4.1.1 Reachstacker (RS)

A reachstacker is a container-handling machine / container lifter / container crane like a crane but at the end of the boom it has a spreader and this way it can lift 20' - 40' empty and full containers (and 45' and 56' containers in 40' position) from 10 to 45 tons up to 6 containers high in the first row. It can even load and unload containers in the second and in the third row. With the rotating spreader the driver can put the container in the right position. Reach stackers can be adapted for any lifting operations in ports, terminals, and stevedoring operations such as container handling.

As reachstackers offer a more efficient and economical solution than any other type of container-handling machine and don't take up too much space, they are widely in operation in many ports and container terminals. Modern reach stackers have an elevating cabin to improve the visibility of the driver.

A special type of reachstacker is the intermodal reachstacker / combi reachstacker. In comparison to the other type of reachstackers it has four extra arms fitted to the spreader called piggy-back. With this extra attachment and with its long wheelbase it can lift and lower laden containers together with the trailer from/onto wagons / railcars on the second rail lift.

Figure 8: Kalmar reachstacker ©KALMAR

4.1.2 Remote control (RC)

Remote operations can improve overall operator performance primarily by extending visibility with multiple camera views. Cameras can be zoomed in on the container and big angles all around the machine can be seen. It helps operators to do the work more efficiently and enhances safety.

Remote operations also serve to improve the working environment for equipment operators by physically removing them from the machines into the safety and comfort of a control room. The control room also

enables a more versatile workplace. If some tasks could be automated, one operator can even operate many machines efficiently from one desk.

There are several benefits to using a remote-controlled container-handling machine, including:

- **Improved Safety:** With a remote-controlled container-handling machine, operators can control the equipment from a safe distance, reducing the risk of injury or accidents.
- **Increased Efficiency:** fewer people, reducing labour costs and increasing productivity when automatic features are available, can operate Remote-controlled container handling machines.
- **Flexibility:** Remote-controlled container handling machines can be operated from a variety of locations, allowing operators to work in different areas and access hard-to-reach spaces.
- **Reduced Downtime:** Remote controlled cargo handling machines can be easily serviced and maintained because of advanced (predictive) monitoring system, reducing downtime and increasing overall equipment reliability.

Within the logistics use case we considered the following scenarios:

- Remote controlled reachstacker (RS): Job order to pick from the stack,
- Remote controlled RS: Job order to place to the stack,
- Remote controlled RS: Job order to pick from the ground,
- Remote controlled RS: Job order to place on the ground,
- Remote controlled RS: Job order to pick from the trailer, and
- Remote controlled RS: Job order to place to the trailer

The following tables report on the collected data on involved agents, workflows and user stories.

Figure 9: Kalmar current Remote Control Desk ©KALMAR

4.2 Names and descriptions of the actors

Name of the actor	Description
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An operator	controls the machine with Remote-Control (RC) desk.
Reachstackers	move containers.
A remote control desk	includes all needed controls and equipment which are needed to operate reachstackers remotely.
Sensors	collect needed measurements for the operator and for the automation system.
Infrastructure	includes components for wireless communication, safety, maintenance, and security.

Table 9: Names and descriptions of the actors UC2

4.3 Logistics use cases

4.3.1 Use Case 2.0: The starting process of the Remote Control (RC) operation

The RC operator arrives at the control center of several machine fleets (they might also be in different geographical locations) and sits at a remote control (RC) desk that is assigned for him and for his shift. The RC operator **logs into the system** by entering his username and password on the login screen.

The RC operator **inspects the RC desk**: he checks with the push button that the RC desk indicator lights are working. In case of malfunction, he contacts service personnel. Then the RC operator activates the RC console with the ACTIVATE button, and a new **connection** between the console and a reachstacker (RS) is established. The system displays the machine operation view. Because it is already dark, the operator switches the **working lights** of the reach stacker ON by pressing the working lights button on the touch screen panel.

The reach stacker is subjected to the first **inspection** of the day (e.g. tires, oil or fuel leaks and whether the engine oil level is sufficient). At the parking area, the maintenance person checks the machine visually. The maintenance person drives with handheld device reachstacker inside operational area. The RC operator starts the operation with RC desk and starts the **engine** of the reach stacker with touch screen panel, if it is not already running. The RC operator checks the status of the machine from the PC screen (alarms, errors and warnings) and videos. The RC operator visually checks with video screens the machines and environmental conditions with cameras attached to the machines and with security cameras attached to lamp posts. Then The RC operator switches the reach stacker to **REMOTE mode**.

Use case name	Remote controlled RS: The starting process of the RC operation
Use case number	UC2.0 Starting process
Summary description	The remote operator logs into the RC desk system, inspects the RC desk, forms a connection with the working machine, switches on the working lights, inspects the condition of the machine, and switches the machine to REMOTE mode.
Status	V2
Stakeholders/actors (primary actor bolded)	1. Remote operator 2. Terminal operating system (TOS) 3. Container position indicator (CPI)
Relevant characteristics (of primary actor)	1. Experienced in remote control of cargo handling machines 2. Container handling knowledge 3. Expertise in port operations
Use case goal	To start operating the machine remotely
Frequency of occurrence	Regularly

Preconditions	1. RC desk is available
	2. Remote operator is available
	3. Machine is ready for operation
Post-Condition(s)	Remote operator has established a connection with the RS, RS is in working condition and in REMOTE mode
Basic flow	1. If the primary joystick is used to navigate menus & select vehicle to connect to, it should provide subtle vibrotactile feedback cues to indicate selection as well as successful connection.
	2. When the connection is established with the RS, the system displays the machine operation view.
	3. The RC operator turns the engine on, notification on the screen
	4. Remote operator inspects the reach stacker visually from camera feed. (Snow and other things, such as damages to the tires, are highlighted.)
	5. Remote operator switches working lights of the reach stacker ON by pressing the working lights button on the touch screen panel, notification on the screen
	6. View from above of the RS provided by several cameras installed in the vehicle garage to support RS operator in inspecting the condition of the RS for snow etc. XR-supported safety warning /AR bounding boxes highlight people and other moving objects if someone (human or machine is arriving close to the area. (Multi-modal support: 6.1. Also, haptics feedback to verify connection is established <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vibrotactile feedback in the primary joystick should confirm connection • Lacking unnecessary degrees-of-freedom, application of joystick base stiffness and damping parameters should indicate successful control connection and functional force feedback. • Vibrotactile warnings should notify the operator if the vehicle is unsuitable for operation or dangerous. 6.2. Also, audio feedback from distance and location before collision Devices: Power wall, normal screen, haptic device, 3D audio device
Alternative flow(s)	1a. Vibrotactile feedback in the primary joystick handle should highlight inbound notifications to the user (e.g. new job available, machine state notification, etc.)
Exceptions	Also, audio feedback from distance and location before collision
	Devices: Power wall, normal screen, haptic device, 3D audio device
Success criteria	Remote operator has established a connection with the RS, RS is in working condition and in REMOTE mode
Challenges and problems	Harsh weather conditions (fog, snow, wind etc.), stability issues, surface quality of ground Maintenance person not available to clean snow, add oil etc. RS fault Engine fault Remote connection fails to be established RC desk fault

Table 10: Use Case 2.0: Remote controlled RS: The starting process of the operation

4.3.2 Use Case 2.1: Pick from the stack

The use case “Remote controlled RS: Job order to pick from the stack” (Table 10) describes which activities are required from which actor to pick sea container from the yard stack where there is adjacent containers around the target container. First, the Terminal Operating System (TOS) sends planned pick job order to the free remote-control desk and remote operator chooses the job from the screen and starts to execute the job. The automation system has already driven the machine near the target position and RC operator’s job is to drive the machine over target position, lower the boom and pick the container and lift it above safe height. The job must be done without collisions against adjacent containers and landing of the spreader should be done smoothly. The user interface and control systems should assist operators to execute the job correctly. The use case is depicted as a use case diagram in Figure 20.

Use case name	Remote controlled RS: Job order to pick from the stack
Use case number	UC2.1
Summary description	The remote operator at RC desk receives the job order, moves RS over the target slot, and picks the container from the stack.
Status	V2
Stakeholders/actors (primary actor bolded)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Remote operator 2. Terminal operating system (TOS) 3. Container position indicator (CPI)
Relevant characteristics (of primary actor)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Experienced in remote control of cargo handling machines 2. Container handling knowledge 3. Expertise in port operations
Use case goal	To pick container without collisions
Frequency of occurrence	Regularly
Preconditions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Valid job order is received from TOS. 2. Remote operator is available 3. Machine is ready for operation
Post-Condition(s)	Container is above safe height and not touching adjacent containers Transportation move
Basic flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shows TOS job order on the PC screen via AR/XR in video feed. E.g. also highlights container location 2. Show to user spreader corners and their distance to the corners of the container below in the stack in video overlay via AR/XR. This will support user to understand if the spreader is correctly located in relation to container underneath and adjacent containers. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If toggled, vibrotactile feedback in the primary joystick should provide additional cues about mean distance between spreader and container corners. 3. Bird view from spreader and container or 3D view of them to support RS operator to lift container without collision. XR-supported safety warning and AR bounding boxes highlight people and other moving objects if someone (human or machine) is arriving close to working area. Multi-modal support: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3.1. Also, haptics feedback to support lifting: Provide vibrotactile and force-feedback indicating collision of the spreader with the container or surrounding objects or containers. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If toggled, force feedback could guide the operator along a sequence of trajectories to best position the spreader above the container for picking.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additional virtual friction could slow the operator when coming close to the ideal contact position, allowing finer positioning and preventing unwanted collisions. • Vibrotactile feedback should indicate successful locking of the twistlocks. • Once the container is picked, added resistance to user motions in the form of damping along the DoFs used for manipulation could confirm to the operator that a load is being handled and provide implicit information about the mass of the load. • Once the container is picked, force or torque feedback applied along the degree of freedom corresponding to container lifting can inform the operator about the mass of the handled load. • Once the container is picked, force feedback could guide the operator along a sequence of trajectories to best retrieve the container from the stack while avoiding any collisions with the environment. • Once the container is picked, vibrotactile feedback can be toggled to provide distance information to surrounding obstacles and warn of imminent collisions <p>3.2. Also, audio feedback from distance and location before collision</p> <p>4. Execution by operator / system</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depending on the input control scheme chosen by the operator, the primary joystick provides a set of degrees-of-freedom (DoF) to enable more ergonomic boom and spreader control. (see deliverable D4.4 for a detailed overview of proposed input control schemes) <p>Devices: Power wall, normal screen, haptic device, 3D audio device</p>
Alternative flow(s)	<p>1a. If the operator drives the spreader, boom or cab to an axis endstop, vibrotactile feedback in the primary joystick can notify the end of range.</p> <p>1b. Vibrotactile warnings in the primary joystick should notify the operator if a load is being handled outside of the recommended range (risk of vehicle imbalance)</p> <p>1c. Force feedback should guide the user back towards the safe region for handling a load if the user goes beyond its boundary (risk of vehicle imbalance)</p> <p>1d. Vibrotactile warnings in the primary joystick should notify the operator in case of unsuccessful twistlock locking</p>
Exceptions	Damaged container can't be picked
Success criteria	Container picked without damages

Challenges and problems	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Harsh weather conditions (fog, snow, wind etc.), stability issues, surface quality of ground. 2. Feedback should not be distracting to the operator: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It must be possible for the operator to toggle all forms of haptic feedback (kinesthetic and vibrotactile). • A UI must be in place for operators to easily acknowledge haptic warnings to avoid unnecessary sensory clutter.
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Table 11: Use Case 2.1: Remote controlled RS: Job order to pick from the stack

Figure 10: Reachstacker picking container from stack ©KALMAR

The machine approaches the container from the front. The RC operator checks on the video screens and AR overlays that there is enough room for extending the spreader and begins to move the spreader into a suitable working position. He chooses the appropriate spreader size by pressing the spreader length button on the touch panel.

He lowers the spreader down towards the container by using the joystick to control the hoist and adjusts the skew using the skew/micro movement joystick. The remaining horizontal and vertical distance between the spreader's twist locks and the corners of the container are visualized on the video screens with AR overlays. The light indicators on the spreader inform the RC operator that the twist locks are safely locked. This allows him to lift the load.

4.3.3 Use Case 2.2: place to the stack

The use case „ Remote controlled RS: Job order to place to the stack” (Table 11) describes which activities are required from which actor to place sea container to the yard stack where there are adjacent containers around the target container. First, the Terminal Operating System (TOS) sends planned place job order to the free remote-control desk and remote operator chooses the job from the screen and starts to execute the job. The automation system has already driven the machine near the target position and RC operator's job is to drive the machine and container over the target position, lower the container on top of the container below and release the spreader and lift spreader above safe height. The job must be done without collisions

against adjacent containers and landing of the container should be done smoothly. The user interface and control systems should assist operator to execute the job correctly. The use case is depicted as a use case diagram in Figure 21.

Use case name	Remote controlled RS: Job order to place to the stack
Use case number	UC2.2
Summary description	The remote operator at RC desk receives the job order, moves RS over the target slot, and places the container on the stack.
Status	V2
Stakeholders/actors (primary actor bolded)	1. Remote operator 2. Terminal operating system (TOS) 3. Container position indicator (CPI)
Relevant characteristics (of primary actor)	1. Experienced in remote control of cargo handling machines 2. Container handling knowledge 3. Expertise in port operations
Use case goal	To place container without collisions
Frequency of occurrence	Regularly
Preconditions	1. Valid job order is received from TOS. 2. Remote operator is available 3. Machine is ready for operation
Post-Condition(s)	Container is landed to correct position Spreader released and spreader above safe height Transportation move
Basic flow	1. Shows TOS job order on the PC screen via AR/XR in video feed. E.g. also highlights container location in relation to container underneath and adjacent containers. 2. Show to user spreader corners and their distance to the corners of the container below in the stack in video overlay via AR/XR. This will support user to understand if the spreader is correctly located. 3. Bird view from spreader and container or 3D view of them to support RS operator to lower container to correct position without collision. XR-supported safety warning / AR bounding boxes highlight people and other moving objects if someone (human or machine) is arriving close to working area. Multi-modal support: 3.1. Also, haptics feedback to support placing container to correct position <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If toggled, vibrotactile feedback should indicate the distance between the bottom of the container and the stack beneath it • If toggled, force feedback could guide the operator along a sequence of trajectories to best position the spreader above the container for placing. • Repulsive force feedback can push the container away from poses which would cause a collision with neighboring containers • Additional virtual friction could slow the operator when coming close to the ideal contact position, allowing finer positioning and preventing unwanted collisions. • Vibrotactile feedback should indicate successful unlocking of the twistlocks.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Once the container is released, any added forces or torques relating to the container manipulation should be removed, implicitly confirming container release to the operator. Provide vibrotactile and force-feedback indicating collision of the container with surrounding objects or containers. <p>3.2. Also, audio feedback from distance and location before collision</p> <p>4. Execution by operator / system</p> <p>Depending on the input control scheme chosen by the operator, the primary joystick provides a set of degrees-of-freedom (DoF) to enable more ergonomic boom and spreader control. (see deliverable D4.4 for a detailed overview of proposed input control schemes)</p>
Alternative flow(s)	<p>1a. If the operator drives the spreader, boom or cab to an axis endstop, vibrotactile feedback in the primary joystick can notify the end of range.</p> <p>1b. Vibrotactile warnings in the primary joystick should notify the operator if a load is being handled outside of the recommended range (risk of vehicle imbalance)</p> <p>1c. Force feedback should guide the user back towards the safe region for handling a load if the user goes beyond its boundary (risk of vehicle imbalance)</p> <p>1d. Vibrotactile warnings in the primary joystick should notify the operator in case of unsuccessful twistlock unlocking</p> <p>Devices: Power wall, normal screen, haptic device, 3D audio device</p>
Exceptions	Twist locks are stuck.
Success criteria	Container placed without damages
Challenges and problems	<p>Harsh weather conditions (fog, snow, wind etc.), stability issues, surface quality of ground.</p> <p>Feedback should not be distracting to the operator:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> It must be possible for the operator to toggle all forms of haptic feedback (kinesthetic and vibrotactile). <p>A UI must be in place for operators to easily acknowledge haptic warnings to avoid unnecessary sensory clutter.</p>

Table 12: Use Case 2.2: Remote controlled RS: Job order to place to the stack

Figure 11: Reachstacker placing container to the stack ©KALMAR

The machine is switched to RC mode (manual). The RC operator positions the spreader with the attached container above the **stack**. He lowers the container and makes fine adjustments using the skew/micro movement joystick. The RC operator uses the camera views and AR overlays to check the correct placing of the container. As the container is lowered onto the stack, The RC operator disengages the twist locks by pressing a button on the joystick and lifts the spreader.

4.3.4 Use Case 2.3: pick from the ground

The use case “Remote controlled RS: Job order to pick from the ground” (Table 13) describes which activities are required from which actor to pick sea container from the yard stack where there are adjacent containers around the target container. First, the Terminal Operating System (TOS) sends planned pick job order to the free remote-control desk and remote operator chooses the job from the screen and starts to execute the job. The automation system has already driven the machine near the target position and RC operator’s job is to drive the machine and spreader over the target position, lower the boom and pick the container and lift it above safe height. The job must be done without collisions against adjacent containers and landing of the spreader should be done smoothly. The user interface and control systems should assist operator to execute the job correctly. The use case is depicted as a use case diagram in Figure 22.

Use case name	Remote controlled RS: Job order to pick from the ground
Use case number	UC2.3
Summary description	The remote operator at RC desk receives the job order, moves RS over the target slot, and picks the container from the ground.
Status	V2
Stakeholders/actors (primary actor bolded)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Remote operator 2. Terminal operating system (TOS) 3. Container position indicator (CPI)
Relevant characteristics (of primary actor)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Experienced in remote control of cargo handling machines 2. Container handling knowledge 3. Expertise in port operations
Use case goal	To pick container without collisions

Frequency of occurrence	Regularly
Preconditions	1. Valid job order is received from TOS.
	2. Remote operator is available
	3. Machine is ready for operation
Post-Condition(s)	Container is above safe height and not touching adjacent containers
	Transportation moves
Basic flow	1. Shows TOS job on the PC screen order via AR/XR in video feed. E.g. also highlights container location
	2. Show to user spreader corners and their distance to the corners of the container below in video overlay via AR/XR. This will support user to understand if the spreader is correctly located in relation to container underneath and adjacent containers. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If toggled, vibrotactile feedback in the primary joystick should provide additional cues about mean distance between spreader and container corners.
	3. Bird view from spreader and container or 3D view of them to support RS operator to lift container without collision. XR-supported safety warning /AR bounding boxes highlight people and other moving objects if someone (human or machine) is arriving close to working area. Multi-modal support:
	3.1. Also, haptics feedback to support lifting <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide vibrotactile and force-feedback indicating collision of the spreader with the container or surrounding objects or containers. • If toggled, force feedback could guide the operator along a sequence of trajectories to best position the spreader above the container for picking. • Additional virtual friction could slow the operator when coming close to the ideal contact position, allowing finer positioning and preventing unwanted collisions. • Vibrotactile feedback should indicate successful locking of the twistlocks. • Once the container is picked, added resistance to user motions in the form of damping along the DoFs used for manipulation could confirm to the operator that a load is being handled and provide implicit information about the mass of the load. • Once the container is picked, force or torque feedback applied along the degree of freedom corresponding to container lifting can inform the operator about the mass of the handled load. • Once the container is picked, force feedback could guide the operator along a sequence of trajectories to best retrieve the container from the stack while avoiding any collisions with the environment. <p>Once the container is picked, vibrotactile feedback can be toggled to provide distance information to surrounding obstacles and warn of imminent collisions</p>
	3.2. Also, audio feedback from distance and location before collision
4. Execution by operator / system <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depending on the input control scheme chosen by the operator, the primary joystick provides a set of degrees-of-freedom (DoF) to enable 	

	<p>more ergonomic boom and spreader control. (see deliverable D4.4 for a detailed overview of proposed input control schemes)</p> <p>Devices: Power wall, normal screen, haptic device, 3D audio device</p>
Alternative flow(s)	<p>1a. If the operator drives the spreader, boom or cab to an axis endstop, vibrotactile feedback in the primary joystick can notify the end of range.</p> <p>1b. Vibrotactile warnings in the primary joystick should notify the operator if a load is being handled outside of the recommended range (risk of vehicle imbalance)</p> <p>1c. Force feedback should guide the user back towards the safe region for handling a load if the user goes beyond its boundary (risk of vehicle imbalance)</p> <p>1d. Vibrotactile warnings in the primary joystick should notify the operator in case of unsuccessful twistlock locking</p>
Exceptions	Damaged container can't be picked
Success criteria	Container picked without damages
Challenges and problems	<p>Harsh weather conditions (fog, snow, wind etc.), stability issues, surface quality of ground.</p> <p>Feedback should not be distracting to the operator:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It must be possible for the operator to toggle all forms of haptic feedback (kinesthetic and vibrotactile). • A UI must be in place for operators to easily acknowledge haptic warnings to avoid unnecessary sensory clutter.

Table 13: Use Case 2.3: Remote controlled RS: Job order to pick from the ground

Figure 12: Reachstacker picking container from the ground. ©KALMAR

4.3.5 Use Case 2.4: Place on the ground

The use case „ Remote controlled RS: Job order to place on the ground” (Table 11) describes which activities are required from which actor to place sea container to the yard stack where there are adjacent containers around the target container. First, the Terminal Operating System (TOS) sends planned place job order to the free remote control desk and remote operator chooses the job from the screen and starts to execute the job. The automation system has already driven the machine near the target position and RC operator’s job is to drive the machine and container over the target position (Marked with painted lines on ground), lower the container on ground and release the spreader and lift spreader above safe height. The job must be done without collisions against adjacent containers and landing of the container should be done smoothly to correct position in relation to painted lines. The user interface and control systems should assist operator to execute the job correctly. The use case is depicted as a use case diagram in Figure 23.

Use case name	Remote controlled RS: Job order to place on the ground
Use case number	UC2.4
Summary description	The remote operator at RC desk receives the job order, moves RS over the target slot, and places the container on the ground
Status	V2
Stakeholders/actors (primary actor bolded)	1. Remote operator 2. Terminal operating system (TOS) 3. Container position indicator (CPI)
Relevant characteristics (of primary actor)	1. Experienced in remote control of cargo handling machines 2. Container handling knowledge 3. Expertise in port operations
Use case goal	To place container without collisions
Frequency of occurrence	Regularly
Preconditions	1. Valid job order is received from TOS. Remote operator is available. 2. Remote operator is available 3. Machine is ready for operation
Post-Condition(s)	Container is landed to correct position Spreader released and spreader above safe height Transportation move
Basic flow	1. Remote operator at RC desk receives job order from TOS. 2. Remote operator moves RS to position appointed by job order, moves spreader and container with the help of CPI over slot and places container according to TOS job order. 3. Remote operator lowers the container and CPI sends grounded message to system. System delivers lift message to TOS.
Alternative flow(s)	1. Operation with over-high folding legs
Exceptions	Twist locks are stuck
Success criteria	Container placed without damages

Challenges and problems	<p>Harsh weather conditions (fog, snow, wind etc.), stability issues, surface quality of ground.</p> <p>Feedback should not be distracting to the operator:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It must be possible for the operator to toggle all forms of haptic feedback (kinesthetic and vibrotactile). <p>A UI must be in place for operators to easily acknowledge haptic warnings to avoid unnecessary sensory clutter.</p>
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Table 14: Use Case 2.4: Remote controlled RS: Job order to place on the ground

Figure 13: Reachstacker placing container to the ground ©KALMAR

XR Flow - How situation unfolds with XR interaction

XR-supported workflow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shows TOS job order on the PC screen via AR/XR in video feed. E.g. also highlights container location 2. Show to user spreader corners in video overlay via AR/XR. This will support user to understand if the spreader is correctly located in relation to adjacent containers or painted lines on ground. 3. Bird view from spreader and container to support RS operator to place container to correct position without collision. XR-supported safety warning /AR bounding boxes highlight people and other moving objects if someone (human or machine) is arriving close to working area. Multi-modal support: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3.1. Also, haptics feedback to support lowering <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If toggled, vibrotactile feedback should indicate the distance between the bottom of the container and the stack beneath it • If toggled, force feedback could guide the operator along a sequence of trajectories to best position the spreader above the container for placing. • Repulsive force feedback can push the container away from poses which would cause a collision with neighboring containers • Additional virtual friction could slow the operator when coming close to the ideal contact position, allowing finer positioning and preventing unwanted collisions. • Vibrotactile feedback should indicate successful unlocking of the twistlocks. • Once the container is released, any added forces or torques relating to the container manipulation should be removed, implicitly confirming container release to the operator.
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide vibrotactile and force-feedback indicating collision of the container with surrounding objects or containers.
	3.2. Also, audio feedback from distance and location before collision
	4. Execution by operator / system
	Depending on the input control scheme chosen by the operator, the primary joystick provides a set of degrees-of-freedom (DoF) to enable more ergonomic boom and spreader control. (see deliverable D4.4 for a detailed overview of proposed input control schemes)
Alternative workflows	<p>1a. If the operator drives the spreader, boom or cab to an axis endstop, vibrotactile feedback in the primary joystick can notify the end of range.</p> <p>1b. Vibrotactile warnings in the primary joystick should notify the operator if a load is being handled outside of the recommended range (risk of vehicle imbalance)</p> <p>1c. Force feedback should guide the user back towards the safe region for handling a load if the user goes beyond its boundary (risk of vehicle imbalance)</p> <p>1d. Vibrotactile warnings in the primary joystick should notify the operator in case of unsuccessful twistlock unlocking</p>
	Devices: Power wall, normal screen, haptic device, 3D audio device

Table 15: XR Flow for Use Case 2.4 (place on the ground)

4.3.6 Use Case 2.5: pick from the trailer

The use case “Remote controlled RS: Job order to pick from the trailer” (Table 17) describes which activities are required from which actor to pick sea container from the trailer where the cabin of the terminal tractor is near container target position. First, the Terminal Operating System (TOS) sends planned pick job order to the free remote control desk and remote operator chooses the job from the screen and starts to execute the job. The automation system has already driven the machine near the target position and RC operator’s job is to drive the machine and spreader over the target container, lower the boom and pick the container and lift it above safe height. The job must be done without collisions against terminal tractor structures and so that the trailer is not lifted together with container. This can happen if container locks are not fully open. The user interface and control systems should assist operator to execute the job correctly. The use case is depicted as a use case diagram in Figure 24.

Use case name	Remote controlled RS: Job order to pick from the trailer
Use case number	UC2.5
Summary description	The remote operator at RC desk receives the job order, moves RS over the trailer and correct slot, and picks the container.
Status	V2
Stakeholders/actors (primary actor bolded)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Remote operator 2. Terminal operating system (TOS) 3. Container position indicator (CPI)
Relevant characteristics (of primary actor)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Experienced in remote control of cargo handling machines 2. Container handling knowledge 3. Expertise in port operations
Use case goal	To pick container without collisions
Frequency of occurrence	Regularly

Preconditions	1. Valid job order is received from TOS.
	2. Remote operator is available
	3. Machine is ready for operation
Post-Condition(s)	Container is above safe height and not touching adjacent containers
	Transportation move
Basic flow	1. Shows TOS job order on the PC screen via AR/XR in video feed. E.g. also highlights container location
	<p>2. Show to user spreader corners and their distance to the corners of the container below in video overlay via AR/XR. This will support user to understand if the spreader is correctly located.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If toggled, vibrotactile feedback in the primary joystick should provide additional cues about the mean distance between spreader and container corners.
	<p>3. Bird view from spreader and container to support RS operator to lift container without collision. XR-supported safety warning /AR bounding boxes highlight people and other moving objects if someone (human or machine is arriving close to working area. Multi-modal support:</p>
	<p>3.1. Also, haptics feedback to support lifting</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement attractive force for precise alignment with the target position • Implement virtual fixtures to guide the operator along a predefined path after a precise alignment is achieved • Provide vibrotactile and force-feedback indicating collision of the spreader with the container or surrounding objects or containers. • If toggled, force feedback could guide the operator along a sequence of trajectories to best position the spreader above the container for picking. • Additional virtual friction could slow the operator when coming close to the ideal contact position, allowing finer positioning and preventing unwanted collisions. • Vibrotactile feedback should indicate successful locking of the twistlocks. • Once the container is picked, added resistance to user motions in the form of damping along the DoFs used for manipulation could confirm to the operator that a load is being handled and provide implicit information about the mass of the load. • Once the container is picked, force or torque feedback applied along the degree of freedom corresponding to container lifting can inform the operator about the mass of the handled load. • Once the container is picked, force feedback could guide the operator along a sequence of trajectories to best retrieve the container from the stack while avoiding any collisions with the environment. • Once the container is picked, vibrotactile feedback can be toggled to provide distance information to surrounding obstacles and warn of imminent collisions • In the event where it is detected that the operator is attempting to lift the container while it is still attached to the terminal tractor, the joystick axis for lifting should be limited by a force-feedback boundary preventing excessive lifting that could cause damage.

	<p>3.2. Also, audio feedback from distance and location before collision</p> <p>4. Execution by operator / system</p> <p>Depending on the input control scheme chosen by the operator, the primary joystick provides a set of degrees-of-freedom (DoF) to enable more ergonomic boom and spreader control. (see deliverable D4.4 for a detailed overview of proposed input control schemes)</p> <p>Devices: Power wall, normal screen, haptic device, 3D audio device</p>
Alternative flow(s)	<p>1a. If the operator drives the spreader, boom or cab to an axis end stop, vibrotactile feedback in the primary joystick can notify the end of range.</p> <p>1b. Vibrotactile warnings in the primary joystick should notify the operator if a load is being handled outside of the recommended range (risk of vehicle imbalance)</p> <p>1c. Force feedback should guide the user back towards the safe region for handling a load if the user goes beyond its boundary (risk of vehicle imbalance)</p> <p>1d. Vibrotactile warnings in the primary joystick should notify the operator in case of unsuccessful twistlock unlocking</p>
Exceptions	Damaged container can't be picked
Success criteria	Container picked without damages
Challenges and problems	<p>Harsh weather conditions (fog, snow, wind etc.), stability issues, surface quality of ground.</p> <p>Feedback should not be distracting to the operator:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It must be possible for the operator to toggle all forms of haptic feedback (kinesthetic and vibrotactile). • A UI must be in place for operators to easily acknowledge haptic warnings to avoid unnecessary sensory clutter.

Table 16: Use Case 2.5: Remote controlled RS: Job order to pick from the trailer

Figure 14: Reachstacker picking container from the trailer ©KALMAR

4.3.7 Use Case 2.6: place to the trailer

The use case “Remote controlled RS: Job order to place to the trailer” (Table 17) describes which activities are required from which actor to place sea container to the trailer where the cabin of the terminal tractor is near container target position. First, the Terminal Operating System (TOS) sends planned place job order to the free remote-control desk and remote operator chooses the job from the screen and starts to execute the job. The automation system has already driven the machine near the target position and RC operator’s job is to drive the machine and container over the target position of the trailer, lower the boom and place the container on trailer on twistlocks, release the spreader and lift the boom above safe height. The job must be done without collisions against terminal tractor structures and so that the trailer is not damaged. The user interface and control systems should assist operator to execute the job correctly. The use case is depicted as a use case diagram in Figure 25.

Use case name	Remote controlled RS: Job order to place to the trailer
Use case number	UC2.6
Summary description	The remote operator at RC desk receives the job order, moves RS over the trailer and correct slot, and places the container.
Status	First draft
Stakeholders/actors (primary actor bolded)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Remote operator 2. Terminal operating system (TOS) 3. Container position indicator (CPI)
Relevant characteristics (of primary actor)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Experienced in remote control of cargo handling machines 2. Container handling knowledge 3. Expertise in port operations
Use case goal	To place container without collisions
Frequency of occurrence	Regularly
Preconditions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Valid job order is received from TOS. Remote operator is available. 2. Remote operator is available 3. Machine is ready for operation

Post-Condition(s)	<p>Container is landed to correct position</p> <p>Spreader released and spreader above safe height</p> <p>Transportation move</p>
Basic flow	<p>1. Shows TOS job order on the PC screen via AR/XR in video feed. E.g. also highlights end-location/optimal route (which the RS follows autonomously in AUTO mode) with AR overlay on the second video feed. Show to user spreader corners and their distance to the corner of the trailer's cabin in video overlay via AR/XR. This will support user to understand if the container is correctly located in relation to the trailer. Also, a simulated 3D LiDAR view of corner castings assists the remote operator in perceiving the distance to the trailer's cabin/corners for correct placement of the container.</p> <p>2. Bird view from spreader and container or 3D view of them to support RS operator to put down the container without collision. User has freedom to choose point of-view e.g., left view. XR-supported safety warning /AR bounding boxes highlight people and other moving objects if someone (human or machine) is arriving close to working area. Multi-modal support:</p> <p>3.1. Also, haptic feedback will support placing container to correct position:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If toggled, vibrotactile feedback should indicate the distance between the bottom of the container and the trailer beneath it • If toggled, force feedback could guide the operator along a sequence of trajectories to best position the spreader above the container for placing. • Repulsive force feedback can push the container away from poses which would cause a collision with neighboring containers • Additional virtual friction could slow the operator when coming close to the ideal contact position, allowing finer positioning and preventing unwanted collisions. • Vibrotactile feedback should indicate successful unlocking of the twistlocks. • Once the container is released, any added forces or torques relating to the container manipulation should be removed, implicitly confirming container release to the operator. • Provide vibrotactile and force-feedback indicating collision of the container with surrounding objects or containers. • In the event where it is detected that the operator is attempting to lift the spreader while it is still attached to the container and the terminal tractor, the joystick axis for lifting should be limited by a force-feedback boundary preventing excessive lifting that could cause damage. <p>3.2. Also, audio feedback from distance and location before collision</p> <p>4. AR or XR view for extra information e.g., distance, speed to put-down of container</p>
Alternative flow(s)	1. Operation with over-high folding legs
Exceptions	Twist locks are stuck
Success criteria	Container picked without damages

Challenges and problems	Harsh weather conditions (fog, snow, wind etc.), stability issues, surface quality of ground
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Table 17: Use Case 2.6: Remote controlled RS: Job order to place to the trailer

Figure 15: Reachstacker placing container to the trailer ©KALMAR

The machine now makes its way to a corridor between the container stacks where it is supposed to load the container onto a truck trailer. The direction of the loading area is also indicated on the video screen.

The system identifies with cameras the truck driver from the video feed by the license plate number that was transmitted via the order. The machine now approaches the trailer for loading up the container.

The machine is switched to RC mode. The RC operator positions the spreader with the attached container **above the trailer. He lowers the container** and makes fine adjustments using the skew/micro movement joystick. The RC operator uses the camera views and AR overlays to check the correct placing of the container. As the container is lowered onto the trailer, The RC operator disengages the twist locks by pressing a button on the joystick and lifts the spreader again.

(While the truck driver walks around the trailer to check the container locks in all four corners, he is highlighted on the video screen.) The RC operator waits until the driver has signaled that everything is fine, then the machine is switched to auto mode and it can head to its next job. The RC operator is checking the camera's video feeds and system status as the machine reverses automatically.

4.3.8 Use Case 2.7: The ending process of the RC operation

The RC operator keeps an eye on the video screens as the reach stacker steers itself back into the vehicle garage. The RC operator sends the vehicle into standby/turns off the engine. The RC operator disconnects the RC table from the RS. Before this, he must check that the job is completed and the RS movements have stopped (there is also a delay for disconnection which assures that the CHE movements have stopped), and that the joysticks are released to the neutral position. Once he has checked these and seeing that that the light on the DISCONNECT button is on (indicating that it is possible to disconnect), he pushes the DISCONNECT button.

(The RC operator looks at his personal performance dashboard on the monitor, which tells him the number of containers he delivered today, his distance driven, the average time per pick-up and placement process

and how his performance compares to his previous workdays. The dashboard tells him that he improved his average pick-up time per container by 5 seconds since last week and by more than 20 seconds since he started working as a professional reach stacker operator just a few weeks ago. The RC operator looks at the job playback, a feature that shows a fast-forward video visualization of the driving path on the port map.)

The RC operator logs out of the vehicle control interface/RC desk.

Use case name	Remote controlled RS: The ending process of the RC operation
Use case number	UC2.7 Ending process
Summary description	The reach stacker steers itself back into the vehicle garage. The remote operator sends the vehicle into standby/turns off the engine of the machine. The remote operator checks the RS movements have stopped and joysticks released to neutral position. The remote operator disconnects the RC table from the RS. (The RC operator checks his personal performance dashboard.) The remote operator logs out of the RC desk.
Status	V2
Stakeholders/actors (primary actor bolded)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Remote operator 2. Terminal operating system (TOS) 3. Container position indicator (CPI)
Relevant characteristics (of primary actor)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Experienced in remote control of cargo handling machines 2. Container handling knowledge 3. Expertise in port operations
Use case goal	To end the remote operation of the RS safely
Frequency of occurrence	Regularly
Preconditions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. RC desk is connected to the RS 2. Job is complete, and machine can steer itself into the garage (AUTO-mode) 3. Machine has stopped its movements
Post-Condition(s)	Remote connection between RC desk and RS ended. RS is in the garage (standby/engine off).
Basic flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Remote operator at RC desk oversees the RS as it steers itself into the garage. The path being driven is visible on the display (AR overlay). 2. The remote operator sends the vehicle into standby/turns off the engine of the machine. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Switching the vehicle to standby drives the force-feedback primary joystick to its neutral position and locks all degrees of freedom, preventing any unwanted control inputs as well as notifying the operator of successful standby. 3. The remote operator checks the RS movements have stopped, and joysticks released to neutral position. 4. The remote operator disconnects the RC table from the RS by pressing the DISCONNECT button. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disconnecting from the reachstacker powers off the force feedback in the primary joystick, leaving all 6 DoF free, implicitly informing operator of successful shutdown. 5. View from above provided by several cameras installed in the vehicle garage to support RS operator. XR-supported safety warning /AR bounding boxes highlight people and other moving objects if someone (human or machine is arriving close to the area. (Multi-modal support: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5.1. Also, haptics feedback to verify connection ended

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Force feedback locking/unlocking of joystick DoF indicates standby / disconnection (see points 2 and 4 above) • Vibrotactile feedback in the primary joystick handle can notify the operator of actions in progress (putting into standby, disconnecting) as well as action conclusion (standby achieved, RS disconnected)
	5.2. Also, audio feedback from distance and location before collision
	6. Job playback: a feature that shows a fast-forward video visualization of the driving path on the port map.
Alternative flow(s)	1. The machine is kept on running while RC operator changes (shift change)
	2. The RC operator checks his personal performance dashboard before logging out of the RC desk.
	5a. In the case of unsuccessful actions or system errors, vibrotactile feedback in the primary joystick handle can warn the operator of these unexpected events.
Exceptions	1. In case of malfunction of the RC desk, the RC operator contacts service personnel.
	2. Reach stacker needs to be cleaned from snow or has tire damage etc. And cannot be driven currently
Success criteria	Remote operator has established a connection with the RS, RS is in working condition and in AUTO mode
Challenges and problems	<p>Harsh weather conditions (fog, snow, wind etc.), stability issues, surface quality of ground</p> <p>Remote connection fails</p> <p>RC desk has a problem (fails to display a notification etc.)</p> <p>Time lag</p>

Table 18: Use Case 2.7: Remote controlled RS: The ending process of the operation

4.4 Use case diagrams

Figure 16: Use case Diagram for “Logistics Use Case 2.1 – Pick container from stack”

Figure 17: Use case Diagram for “Logistics Use Case 2.2 – Place container to stack”

Figure 18: Use case Diagram for “Logistics Use Case 2.3 – Pick container from ground”

Figure 19: Use case Diagram for “Logistics Use Case 2.4 – Place container on ground”

Figure 20: Use case Diagram for “Logistics Use Case 2.5 – Pick container from the trailer”

Figure 21: Use case Diagram for “Logistics Use Case 2.6 – Place container to the trailer”

4.5 User stories

ID	PRIORITY	AS A [type of user]	I NEED TO [do some task]	SO THAT I CAN [get some result]	STATUS	UC 2.1	UC 2.2	UC 2.3	UC 2.4	UC 2.5	UC 2.6
2.1	Must have	Remote RS-Operator	get information about target slot position (X; Y, Tier)	move RS spreader over target slot	Open	X	X	X	X	X	X

2.2	Must have	Remote RS-Operator	get information about target container	select the correct size of the spreader and check that I have correct spreader attachment	Open	x		x		x	
2.3	Must have	Remote RS-Operator	get closed information from spreader	pick up the container and lift it above safe height	Open	x		x		x	
2.4	Must have	Remote RS-Operator	get landed and twist locks open information from spreader	lift spreader over safe height after container landing	Open		x		x		x
2.5	Must have	Remote RS-Operator	get warning if adjacent containers are close to spreader or hanging container	avoid collision	Open		x		x		x
2.6	Must have	Remote RS-Operator	get information about distance under spreader / container to container underneath or ground	avoid collision and enable soft landing	Open		x		x		x
2.7	Should have	Remote RS-Operator	get information about obstacles near RS	avoid collisions and accidents	Open	x	x	x	x	x	x
2.8	Must have	Remote RS-Operator	get information about machine's status and health	to continue operation efficiently without breaks	Open	x	x	x	x	x	x
2.9	Must have	Remote RS-Operator	get information about relative position between container/spreader or container/container	to pick up or land container efficiently	Open	x	x	x	x	x	x

Table 19: User Stories for Logistics Use Cases

4.6 Issues

The following issues have been depicted:

- Visibility to target position and container
- Visibility to obstacles around the machine (blind spots because of mechanical structures)
- Distances between objects needs to be rather small in some cases
- Trailer twist locks can get stuck
- Material damages (containers, infrastructure, etc.)
- Safety (persons around the machine and other vehicles)

- Productivity of the remote-controlled system needs automated features
- Latency time and reliability of the communication

5 Use case 3 – Construction

5.1 Description of the system

In the field of construction machinery, the excavator is one of the most common machines with a wide variety of designs. A typical application for an excavator is earthmoving in civil engineering and landscaping. Modern excavators feature a so-called 3D-machine control system, which is a sensor system that measures the kinematic information of the attachment as well as the high-precision position with an RTK-GNSS.

With the help of a 3D-machine control system and a digital terrain model, the operator can align its working process with the digital design model. This paves the way for the comprehensive implementation of model-based construction (BIM) but may challenge the operators with increased complexity and automation in novel and more dynamic information spaces that require advanced forms of information presentation and interaction. Figure 26 shows an excavator with a 3D-machine control system. The two displays inside the cabin show video streams of the surrounding areas and the digital 3D-model of the excavator.

Figure 22: An excavator with a 3D-machine control system and a bird-view camera setup in order to monitor the danger areas close to the machine (© ÜAZ Glauchau, Bau Bildung Sachsen e. V.)

Within the construction use case we considered three scenarios:

- Finish Grading (target surface profile),
- Collision Avoidance (with persons or objects), and
- Infield Design.

The following tables report on the collected data on involved agents, workflows and user stories.

5.2 Names and descriptions of the actors

Name of the actor	Description
A machine operator	controls the excavator and the 3D-machine-control system.
A survey assistant	sets reference points in the working area to mark the target design.
A person in the danger	standing in the danger area of the excavator and might be hit accidentally by the excavator.

Table 20: Name and descriptions of the actors Use Case 3

5.3 Construction use cases

5.3.1 Use Case 3.1

The use case “Finish Grading” describes the activities by the operator which are related to creating a level plane or a slope with high demands on precision. After checking of the general system, the operator must set the reference height of the desired surface. This can be done either by using a predefined digital design model that is chosen from the UI or by setting the reference height manually in the UI. Afterwards, the operator must check if the model aligns with the real environment. If everything is correct, the operator starts digging to make a rough level pass. Therefore, holes are filled, and hills are removed. Finally, the operator performs a finish grading by moving the edge of the bucket according to the final design specification. The use case is depicted as a use case diagram in Figure 27 and is described in the subsequent table.

Use case name	Finish Grading (target surface profile)
Use case number	3.1
Summary description	Making a finish grade with an excavator (plane, ramp)
Status	Medium level of detail
Stakeholders/actors (primary actor bolded)	1. Operator
Relevant characteristics (of primary actor)	1. experienced operator, skilled in excavator handling
	2. Mapping between real environment and 3D representation, understanding how 3D control works
	3. Basic knowledge of soil behaviour and civil works
	4. Basic knowledge of environmental factors on soil behaviour (humidity, weather, wind)
Use case goal	1. Create a Finish Grading with a reference height on bare soil
Frequency of occurrence	Regularly
Preconditions/Requirements	1. Irregular soil surface (probably after cleaning of rocks and tree stumps)
	2. A 20t excavator with a bucket.
	3. A 3D machine control system.
Post-Condition(s)	1. The surface is levelled out according to reference height (Accuracy = 5cm)
Basic flow	2. Final surface profile is logged/measured and documented as a DTM (digital terrain model)
	1. Check general machine status und check 3d-machine control system status.
	2. Check target surface profile, determine own position
	3. Set the reference height for the finish plane: a) set height in GNNS System (b) tip with bucket to set height relative to object (e.g. road curb) in environment c) working together with a separate person who surveys road with GNSS-Rover
	3. Develop a grading strategy (where to start, where to move, and how to finish, consider working area boundaries, soil reservoirs or dump areas, logistic areas and paths)
	4. Fill holes and level out bumps by moving soil with the bucket.
5. Move vehicle to change action radius	

	6. Work together and communicate with crawler or truck
	7. Create a uniform plane (level pass) with the teeth of the bucket.
	8. Finish the grading by smoothing out the ground with the bottom plate of the bucket.
Alternative flow(s)	1. There is too much material to reach reference height. Material must be removed.
Exceptions	1. There is a lack of material to reach reference height.
Success Criteria	1. Accuracy
	2. Time/Speed
	3. Gentle use of machine and tool
Challenges and Problems	1. Requires good handling skills especially for linear movements of the bucket.
	2. Requires planning of soil distribution and backfilling.
	3. Requires confident usage of 3D-machine control system.
	4. Spatial imagination to reference virtual model with real references.

Table 21: Use Case 3.1: Finish Grading (target surface profile)

XR Flow - How situation unfolds with XR interaction

Advanced flow	1. Check general machine status und check 3D-machine control system status.
	2. Set the reference height for the finish plane: a) set height in GNSS System (b) tip with bucket to set height relative to object (e.g., road curb) in environment c) working together with a separate person who surveys road with GNSS-Rover
	3. XR: reference height is visualized in alignment with real environment
	4. XR: show delta of target and actual height and boundaries, show where to move material to easily develop a grading strategy
	5. Fill holes and level out bumps by moving soil with the bucket.
	6. Create a uniform plane (level pass) with the teeth of the bucket.
	7. Finish the grading by smoothing out the ground with the bottom plate of the bucket.

Table 22: XR Flow for Construction Use case 3.1

5.3.2 Use Case 3.2

Use case 3.2. is about collision avoidance during everyday working tasks. The excavator has multiple blind spots which results in a risk of hitting persons within these danger zones during operation. The excavator is usually equipped with a camera monitor system (CMS), which displays video streams of the blind spots on a display inside the cabin. As an extension, the CMS is enhanced with a collision warning systems, which informs the operator about persons in the danger zone. Before critical movements, the operator can check the video streams. The operator can either detect or oversee an obstacle, even after a warning of the collision warning system. The detection of an obstacle results leads to a stopping motion and the operator must contact the person in the danger zone. If the operator oversees the person, the risk of hitting the person is high during a critical movement, e.g., while slewing. The person in the danger zone is responsible for leaving the surrounding of the machine as soon as possible. Although the collision warning system and the CMS are helpful to monitor the surrounding, it might warn to frequently which leads to annoyance of the operator. The use case is depicted as a use case diagram in Figure 28 and is described in the subsequent table.

Use case name	Collision Avoidance (with persons or objects)
Use case number	3.2
Summary description	Ensure that there will be no collision at the rear and at the side of the excavator while slewing.
Status	Medium level of detail
Stakeholders/actors (primary actor bolded)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Operator A person standing in the slewing radius Operators of other vehicles in the area
Relevant characteristics (of primary actor)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Basic knowledge about machines dimensions and clearance General environmental awareness Familiarity with distorted perspective in mirrors and mirror replacement camera images Knowledge about safe working on construction sites
Use case goal	<p>Stop Slewing when there is a collision obstacle.</p> <p>The person standing in the slewing radius is informed about the excavator's movement and leaves the danger zone</p> <p>Collision avoided</p>
Frequency of occurrence	Often
Preconditions/Requirements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Operator is working concentrated. An unexpected slewing motion has to be done. The excavator has a camera monitor system (CMS) at the right side and at the rear of the machine. The CMS has a collision warning system (CWS) and actively warns the operator.
Post-Condition(s)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> The excavator stopped the slewing movement. Persons in the way have left the danger zone
Basic flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> The operator starts the machine and checks that it is ready for use. The operator drives to the working position. The operator starts the working procedure (e.g., trenching) The operator digs in the centre line and swings 45° to the left for unloading. This procedure is continued. The operator wants to swing to the right (e.g., to change the attachment) The operator checks the rear and side of the machine before slewing via CMS. The operator detects the person within the danger area. The operator does not initiate the slewing movement and informs the person to move out of the way
Alternative flow(s)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> The operator performs the slewing movement without previous check of the blind spots. The operator checks the CMS but does not see the person in the danger zone. The operator hits the person <p>1. The operator checks the rear and side of the machine before slewing via CMS.</p>

	2. The person standing in the slewing radius perceives the intent to move the excavator
	3. The person standing in the slewing radius leaves the danger zone
	1. The ODS detects the obstacle and warns the operator.
	2. The operator stops the movement and informs the person.
	1. The operator is annoyed by the ODS and disables the warnings.
	2. The operator hits the person.
Exceptions	No obstacle detected or object falsely detected
Success Criteria	1. No damage, no harm, no casualties
	2. Time lost in machine blockage
	3. No abrupt stops
	4. Persons in the area increase awareness of vehicles movements
Challenges and Problems	1. Reliable detection of (fast) objects and persons in proximity
	2. Detection of type of obstacle
	3. Detection of severity of object approach (in detection range but in safe distance - too close)
	4. Do not annoy the operator by any active obstacle warnings.

Table 23: Use Case 3.2: Collision Avoidance (with persons or objects)

XR Flow - How situation unfolds with XR interaction

Advanced flow	1. The operator starts the machine and checks that it is ready for use.
	2. The operator drives to the working position.
	3. The operator starts the working procedure (e.g., trenching)
	4. The operator digs in the centre line and swings 45° to the left for unloading. This procedure is continued.
	5. The operator wants to swing to the right (e.g., to change the attachment)
	6. The CWS detects a person in the slewing area.
	7. XR technology helps to perceive the obstacle when the operator moves into this direction (ambient light which indicates direction and risk of potential collisions in an intuitive way).
	8. The operator notices the indication for potential collisions and checks the video stream.
	9. The operator does not initiate the slewing movement.

Table 24: XR Flow for Construction Use case 3.2

5.3.3 Use Case 3.3

The use case “Infield Design” describes the task of designing a digital terrain model during operation with the on-board machine control system and without usage of predefined digital models. After checking the operability of the system, the operator should drive to the working position and use the UI to start the infield design process. The operator must set the outline of the pit by moving the bucket to the desired position. Then, the operator sets the profile of the pit with the help of the UI. The referenced outline points are usually setup by a survey assistant e.g. by setting surveyor’s stakes in the soil. Afterwards, the operator verifies the created model with respect to the real environment and start the digging. The use case is depicted in the use case diagram in Figure 29 and is described in the following table.

Use case name	Infield Design
Use case number	3.3
Summary description	Create a pit design model on site
Status	Medium level of detail
Stakeholders/actors (primary actor bolded)	1. operator 2. surveyor assistant
Relevant characteristics (of primary actor)	1. Basic knowledge on geometry 2. Basic knowledge on civil works and soil behaviour 3. spatial imagination skills
Use case goal	Create a DTM (digital terrain model) for pit excavation on site.
Frequency of occurrence	Occasionally
Preconditions/Requirements	1. excavator with bucket and 3D-machine control system 2. reference points set up by surveyor assistant 3. area is free of obstacles
Post-Condition(s)	A correctly referenced DTM
Basic flow	1. The operator starts the machine and checks that it is ready for use. 2. The operator drives to the working position. 3. The operator checks if the 3D-system is operational and with high precision. 4. The operator navigates the GUI to set up an infield design by outline and profile. 5. The operator sets the outline of the pit by inserting the reference points manually. 6. The operator sets profile (slope angle, base area) of the pit 7. The operator checks the resulting model 8. The operator moves the excavator in the 3D-model visualization to check if model and environment are aligned as expected.
Alternative flow(s)	1. The operator sets the outline by referencing the marker posts. 2. The operator sets the outline by reference to a virtual 3D model.
Exceptions	-
Success Criteria	1. Correctness of DTM 2. Time on task
Challenges and Problems	1. complex operations and information required for 3D model manipulations 2. mapping of virtual model to real environment

Table 25: Use Case 3.3: Infield Design

XR Flow - How situation unfolds with XR interaction

Advanced flow	1. The operator starts the machine and checks that it is ready for use.
	2. The operator drives to the working position.
	3. The operator checks if the 3D-system is operational and with high precision.
	4. The operator navigates the GUI to set up an infield design by outline and profile.
	5. The operator sets the outline of the pit by inserting the reference points manually.
	6. XR-support: The reference points are visualized with alignment to the real environment on the main screen. The actual environment is shown as a height-map with textures. The design model is aligned to this representation of the surrounding.

	7. The operator sets profile (slope angle, base area) of the pit
	8. XR-support: The outline is visualized with alignment to the real environment
	9. XR: The resulting height difference between model and surrounding is visualized.
Alternative flow(s)	1. The operator sets the outline by referencing the marker posts.
	2. The operator sets the outline by reference to a virtual 3D model.

Table 26: XR Flow for Construction Use case 3.3

5.4 Use case diagrams

Figure 23: Use case Diagram for “Construction Use Case 3.1. - Finish Grading”

Figure 24: Use case Diagram for “Construction Use Case 3.2. - Collision Avoidance”

Figure 25: Use case Diagram for “Construction Use Case 3.3. - Infield Design” User stories

5.5 User Stories

The user stories describe tasks of different priorities which must be handled by relevant users. For the construction use cases, the user stories are presented in Table 29.

ID	PRIORITY	AS A [type of user]	I NEED TO [do some task]	SO THAT I CAN [get some result]	STATUS	UC 3.1	UC 3.2	UC 3.3
3.1	Must have	Operator	get a clear indication of the system status	rely on the functionality or understand malfunction	Open	x	x	x
3.2	Must have	Operator	get a clear indication of the reference between virtual model and reality	work in the proper area	Open	x		x
3.3	Must have	Operator	Move the bucket according to target design	Make the finish grade efficiently and fast	Open	x		
3.4	Must have	Operator	Overview the whole working area and the height difference between target design and real surface	Plan the soil distribution	Open	x		x
3.5	Must have	Operator	Model a digital terrain model in field	Work with a 3D-control system	Open	x		x
3.6	Must have	Operator	Observe the blind spots on the right and rear	Detect potential collisions and stop dangerous manoeuvres	Open	x	x	
3.7	Must have	Operator	Recognize obstacles and persons in blind spots	Avoid collisions	Open	x	x	

Table 27: User Stories for construction Use Cases

5.6 Issues

The following issues have been depicted:

- The operator's view on the attachment and the graphical user interface are not in one visual axis.
- Current 3D-machine control interfaces offer a visual display of target and actual bucket height. It hardly allows a comprehensive view of the entire work area to plan e.g., backfilling.
- Current operation requires confident usage and understanding of 3D-machine control systems and confidence in proper alignment of 3D-model to real world.
- Spatial imagination to align the abstract, virtual reference model with real references.
- Infield design requires a spatial imagination to design profile and outline with reference to the real environment.
- Collision Warning Systems often annoy the operator due to the high frequency of warnings. This leads to deactivation of CWS.

6 Status of operator validation

The use cases and possible solutions described here are currently being studied within the transdisciplinary co-design process, as presented in D3.1/3.6 and D3.2. Following initial ideation workshops to collect technically feasible solution ideas, vision scenarios have been developed to discuss possible future interaction flows with vehicle operators (see D3.2). The vision scenarios, which outline the future use of XR technologies in common use case tasks (scenarios listed in 3.1, 4.1 and 5.1), have been validated and partly extended in the co-design process with operators. This process is ongoing, but to the current day, twelve XR application concepts in total have already been approved by operators (five in UC1, three in UC2, four in UC3), see Table 28. More are currently under investigation.

Use case	Operator-approved XR application concept
Snow grooming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ambient light bars around the windscreen with moving, glowing areas of different sizes and colours to indicate, e. g., vehicle health or AI-detected objects in vicinity • Highlighting target slope area in real time on onboard display based on digital slope model, possibly coupled with laser or light projections on the ground • Real-time laser projection of auxiliary lines indicating vehicle dimensions (for moving in tight spaces) and overlap with previously groomed lanes • Three-dimensional real-time visualization of current vehicle position and alignment on the slope on onboard screen • Display-based and/or laser projection of navigation indicators
Logistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Navigation indicators on top of (VR or monitor-based) camera view • Auxiliary projections on top of camera view facilitating container pick-up and placement, indicating correct spreader alignment with container and twist lock status • Visualization of container dimensions and projected turning areas on ground
Construction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognition of excavation pit markings in the real world and automatic processing into the digital terrain model • Display-based visualization of the type and position of power lines and AI-detected objects in the work area on top of camera view • Laser projection of excavation pit boundaries, power lines etc., and optional auxiliary visualizations (e. g., minimum distance to excavation pit based on vehicle weight) • Ambient light bars around the windscreen with moving, glowing areas of different sizes and colours to indicate, e. g., AI-detected objects in the vicinity, distance of the bucket corners (left and right) to the target surface of the excavation pit

Table 28: Operator-approved XR application concepts in use cases

7 Conclusions

Our use cases describe the utilization of XR extensions in specific heavy machinery use cases: snowgroomer, reachstacker and excavator.

We decided to utilize user stories to describe especially the operator's role in the process. User stories are centred on the result and the benefit of the thing you're describing, whereas Use Cases can be more granular, and describe how your system will act. We also listed potential issues which we found during this phase.

We also utilized use case diagrams, which model the behaviour of a system and help to capture the requirements of the system. Use case diagrams describe the high-level functions and scope of a system. These diagrams also identify the interactions between the system and its actors.

This document is modified based on requirement specification and technical analysis. This document is also based on XR system design and implementation work done so far. This document is updated version of the deliverable 2.1.

In the snow grooming use case, the most important aspect is to support the human operator when there is limited visibility, so that there is knowledge about the environment that is not visible.

In logistics use cases it is important to assist the remote controller to avoid material damages like pushing dents or even holes to adjacent containers with handled container. Also, twistlocks of the trailer can be stuck if the road truck driver is not careful enough when opening locks. The most important aspect in logistic use case is to avoid safety issues with novel obstacle avoidance system.

Finally, within the construction use case it is important that the information is provided in the view of the operator while working at a task. Additionally, obstacle avoidance is, as in all the use case, one of the main important aspects.

8 Abbreviations / Acronyms

[BIM]	Building Information Modelling
[CHE]	Container handling equipment
[CMS]	Camera-Monitor-System
[CPI]	Container position indicator
[CWS]	Collision Warning System
[DTM]	Digital Terrain Model
[GNSS]	Global Navigation Satellite System
[HMI]	Human-Machine-Interfaces
[OEM]	Original Equipment Manufacturer
[RC]	Remote Control
[RS]	Reach Stacker
[RTK]	Real Time Kinematic
[TOS]	Terminal operating system
[UC]	Use Case
[UML]	Unified Modelling Language
[WP]	Work Package
[XR]	Extended Reality